

A Revista Angolana de Ciências da Saúde como contributo para a investigação científica de Angola

The Angolan Journal of Health Sciences as a contribution to scientific research of Angola

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Scientific articles published in scientific journals contribute to safeguarding the knowledge recorded in it, in addition to serving as a means of communication between researchers and the dissemination of research results¹. We cannot continue to develop this editorial without unraveling the word “investigate” that comes from the Latin “investigare” in which the Portuguese-language dictionaries bring us the definitions of: following the traces of, inquiring, researching, inquiring.

It is very common to hear the expression: “it is important to investigate on health field” the question that could be made is: why? or otherwise when investigating the benefit is for the patient or the health professional?

As defended by IJsselmuiden and Matlin², unfortunately, the essence of investing in health research is not yet understood, given the continuing scarcity of financial resources ment for this purpose. Therefore, investing in health research in developing countries is a necessity, not an extravagance, as people aspire to a full and healthy life despite economic disparities. The money spent on health research is an economic impeller, increases competitiveness and addresses the social determinants of health.

Although often misrepresented, health research is not only aimed at generating knowledge, discovering best practices and eliminating barriers to care, more than that, it must lead to action. In a singular way, the results of the research should guide the development of policies and programs, as well as the provision of health services. Interventions must be based on evidence and based on solid research^{3, 4}.

There are numerous case studies done at different levels on the benefits of health research. At the same time, it is recognized the importance of health research for the exercise of the profession, making appropriate and effective decisions, providing better care to patients, developing critical capacity and consequently demonstrating to other professionals the fundamentals on which the practice of healthcare is established for each professional.

According to Unit for Sight³, the evidence suggests that patients who receive care in hospitals with research activities have better health outcomes. Due to the fact that the hospital with research activities is able to offer broader treatment options and more opportunities for inclusion in clinical studies.

The availability of health information can guarantee funding and promoting the effectiveness of interventions. The research defines indicators and collects health metrics in addition to being an integral part of obtaining better results. They allow decision-makers and donors to assess progress towards desired goals and best practices³. For McAllister⁵, the research should focus on the concerns raised by developing countries, eliminating not only the gap in disparities in health levels within countries, but also the knowledge gap between the developed and the developing world.

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Thus, there are numerous contexts in which health professionals can be involved in research, whether as researchers, coordinating studies or as part of the research team and / or as users of research results.

Another drawback is that, unfortunately, high-quality health information is not widely available in underdeveloped and developing countries, as a result, results are often not measured by international organizations and there is not a real picture of the health situation.

The data speaks for itself, from the quantitative survey of the number of scientific journals in Angola made by Chitumba⁶, until December 2020, from 17 journals, 7 were edited by public institutions and only 2 were specifically dedicated to the publication of scientific articles in the area of health sciences. Considering that the essence of the investigation is to make the results from there public, the data presented above do not require comments and lead us to a deep reflection and clear and urgent need to develop scientific culture as a criterion of truth, with persistence and continuity, starting with training of health professionals creating in them the taste and spirit of research, a statement supported by Bettencourt Mateus⁷. For example, in some countries the attention that is devoted to scientific research is part of the evaluation of health professionals in health institutions as a way to encourage research⁸.

Given the above, as a contribution to scientific research in the field of health in Angola, with the aim of giving greater access to national scientific production and beyond, as well as giving visibility to the research carried out by students, teaching doctors, researchers, staff connected to the health area and beyond, helping them in decision-making, on July 30, 2020, headed by a professor from the Faculty of Medicine of Huambo of the Jose Eduardo dos Santos University. A Multidisciplinary Team of health professionals and national researchers, made public the Angolan Journal of Health Sciences, also known as RACSAÚDE³.

The Angolan Journal of Health Sciences is a peer-reviewed journal that adopts international standards of suitable institutions in its editorial process. RACSAÚDE aims at being recognized as a health sciences journal of great impact at national and international level, to make Africa and the world aware of the reality of the current health situation and the advances in research at national and international level, in addition to promoting the highest quality scientific publication.

On this path, we would sin deeply if we finished without thanking in a special way to all doctors, professors and national and international researchers who, on time and without measuring efforts, joined the invitation to embark on this great trip.

Given the context and by editorial decision, this first edition was dedicated only to the launch of this editorial and a dissertation abstract that talk about the historical evolution of the Angolan national health system covering the first Volume. Thus, another scientific journal in the field of health sciences is born, as a way of contributing to national scientific research.

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